

Across time analysis of morphological and physiological traits in grassland plant mixtures versus monocultures

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Summary

In Portugal, the DIVERSify project focused on evaluating the effect of plant-plant interactions on the overall performance of grassland mixtures. Four biodiverse plant mixtures and their individual species components morphological and physiological traits were compared under growth chamber conditions to identify key mechanisms in mixtures' performance. Mixtures included different combinations of 4–6 species from *Leguminosae* and *Gramineae* families. Root and the aerial fraction dry weight, the leaf area, and leaf turgid and dry weight were the most differentiating traits both among plant mixtures and the legume species. Mixtures additionally differentiated among themselves by specific leaf area, root length, and secondary root length. The plant mixtures occupied an intermediate position between the clovers (*Trifolium*) and the grasses individual components, mainly due to the influence of canopy height and plant length traits.

These results provide new information for breeding innovative grassland mixtures with optimised resource utilisation, aiming at a productive and stress resilient agriculture.

Key words: Grassland, biodiverse mixtures, physiological and morphological traits, legumes, cereals, breeding targets

Introduction

Biodiversity in Mediterranean grasslands is seriously affected by climate change (Henkin *et al.*, 2010). Environmental changes also have an impact on grassland productivity and composition, as well as on the role of each individual species in the mixture (van Oijen *et al.*, 2018). A high level of biodiversity may confer stability to grassland and may be crucial for the longer-term resilience of ecosystems in response to environmental change with species-rich communities tending to perform better than individual species (Oliver *et al.*, 2015).

Fertiprado, a Portuguese seed company, has been developing plant mixtures rich in legumes and grasses species, adapted to different soil and climatic conditions of grassland and pasture production areas. The aim of this study was to evaluate and compare morphological and physiological traits of four of these biodiverse plant mixtures and their individual species components across time. This will enable the identification of potential breeding targets related to beneficial plant-plant species interactions and niche complementarities that may support the optimization of plant team mixtures to cope better with future climatic constraints.

Materials and Methods

Four commercial biodiverse plant mixtures were used in this study. The mixtures included different combinations of 4–6 of nine plant species, from *Leguminosae* (*Trifolium incarnatum*, *T. michelianum*, *T. suaveolens*, *T. squarrosus*, *T. vesiculosum*, *Vicia villosa*), and *Gramineae* families (*Lolium multiflorum* (2n and 4n), *Avena strigosa*, and *Triticosecale*). The mixtures and their individual plant species components were morphological and physiologically compared at “mesocosm” level (0.15 m² pots), in a growth chamber mimicking field environmental conditions during southern interior Portuguese autumn (temperature 20°C day 14°C night; photoperiod 11 h; relative humidity 60%; light intensity ~200–300 μmol m⁻² s⁻¹).

Measurements started 3 weeks after germination and were performed weekly until the 7th week. Weekly measured traits were canopy height, plant length, aerial fraction dry weight, root fraction dry weight, dry shoot to dry root ratio, root and secondary root lengths, plant dry weight, biomass (=plant dry weight)/hectare, and root fraction dry weight per hectare. The final week of measurements also included the destructive assessment of chlorophylls a and b, total carotenoids content, leaf area, specific leaf area, leaf dry and turgid weights per cm² and per leaf area, and leaf dry matter content.

Multivariate principal components analysis was performed using the adjusted mean values obtained from linear mixed models. To stabilise the traits variance, the Box-Cox procedure was conducted and the most appropriate transformation applied. All statistical analyses were conducted using Gentstat[®] software (Payne *et al.*, 2015).

Results

Fig. 1. Principal component analysis of morphological data measured across time of four mixtures and nine different annual forage species, with the indication of the time of measurement (weeks after germination, WAG). The two principal components accounted for 82.56% of the total variation.

Table 1. Description of the traits measured, with the indication of the trait abbreviations used in the principal components analysis. The loading values of the two first principal components (PC1 and PC2) are also shown. The suffix “Tran” in the trait abbreviations indicates that the trait was transformed

Trait abbreviations	Trait description	Units	PC1	PC2
Ca	Chlorophyll a content	mg cm ⁻²	0.284309	0.100457
Ca/Cb	Chlorophylls a/b ratio		0.238431	-0.0041
Ca+Cb	Chlorophyll a + chlorophyll b	mg cm ⁻²	0.279013	0.073775
Ca+Cb/Ccx	Chlorophylls/carotenoids ratio		0.115812	0.409811
Ca+CbDWTan	chlorophyll a + chlorophyll b expressed by dry weight	mg g ⁻¹	0.290032	-0.06385
CaDWTan	Chlorophyll a content expressed by dry weight	mg g ⁻¹	0.295466	-0.0354
Cb	Chlorophyll b content	mg cm ⁻²	0.278608	0.136936
CbDWTan	Chlorophyll b content expressed by dry weight	mg g ⁻¹	0.297005	-0.03578
Ccx	Total carotenoids content	mg cm ⁻²	0.288034	-0.00981
CcxDWTan	Total carotenoids content expressed by dry weight	mg g ⁻¹	0.28855	-0.13939
DW1	Leaf dry weight cm ²	g cm ⁻²	-0.22574	0.365123
DWLATan	Dry weight per leaf area	g cm ⁻²	0.119609	0.399572
LAR	Leaf area	mm ²	0.237111	0.148659
LDMCTan	Leaf dry matter content	mg g ⁻¹	-0.20678	-0.06215
SLA	Specific leaf area	mm ² mg ⁻¹	0.213314	-0.28868
TW1Tan	Turgid weight per cm ²	g cm ⁻²	-0.15307	0.47663
TWLA	Turgid weight per leaf area	g cm ⁻²	0.185479	0.377055
ADW _{ha} Tan	Aerial fraction dry weight ha ⁻¹	g ha ⁻¹	0.27535	0.25977
ADW _{kg_{ha}} Tan	Aerial fraction dry weight ha ⁻¹	kg ha ⁻¹	0.27535	0.25977
ADWTan	Aerial fraction dry weight	g	0.27535	0.25977
B _{ha} Tan	Biomass/hectare	g ha ⁻¹	0.294349	0.136884
B _{kg_{ha}} Tan	Biomass/hectare	kg ha ⁻¹	0.294349	0.136884
CH	Canopy height	cm	0.230038	-0.32049
DRLTan	Dry root weight root length ratio	g cm ⁻²	0.181479	0.149826
PDWTan	Plant dry weight	g	0.294349	0.136884
PL	Plant length	cm	0.181422	-0.41737
RDW _{ha} Tan	Root fraction dry weight ha ⁻¹	g ha ⁻¹	0.2886	-0.04614
RDW _{kg_{ha}} Tan	Root fraction dry weight ha ⁻¹	kg ha ⁻¹	0.281444	-0.05967
RDWTan	Root fraction dry weight	g	0.2886	-0.04614
RLTan	Root length	cm	0.243799	-0.20425
S/DTan	Dry shoot to dry root ratio		-0.10092	0.50898
SRLTan	Secondary root length	cm	0.240652	-0.07192
SRRL	Secondary root length to root length ratio		-0.14328	0.358069

Fig. 2. Principal component analysis of morphological measurements of four mixtures (diamonds) and nine different annual forage species (circles), 7 weeks after germination. The two principal components accounted for 79.80% of the total variation.

There was a clear separation between *Gramineae* and *Leguminosae* species across time by canopy height (CH) and aerial and root dry weight ratio (S/D), with *A. strigosa* being the tallest species, with the smallest S/D value (Fig. 1). Among the legume species, separation was clear by plant length (PL), and by aerial and root dry weight fractions (ADW, RDW), with *V. villosa* showing the highest values and *T. incarnatum* the smallest. The four mixtures were also differentiated by the root dry weight (RDW), the aerial dry weight (ADW), and overall biomass, which were bigger for mixture 2 and 3. A description of the traits, including the measurements units and the loadings of the principal components analysis are included in Table 1.

Seven weeks after germination and looking at the destructive measures taken, the plant mixtures occupied an intermediate position between the legumes (especially the *Trifolium* spp.) and the grasses (Fig. 2). Overall, the legume species had higher photosynthetic pigments content when compared with the grasses. Mixture 2 showed higher values of leaf dry and turgid weights, and slightly higher values of photosynthetic pigments content than the other mixtures. Although mixture 1 had an inferior photosynthetic pigments content when compared to the other mixtures and legume species, it was positioned towards the direction of the leaf dry matter content (LDMC) vector, close to *L. multiflorum* 2n. LDMC also separated the remaining grasses from the legume species and the remaining mixtures.

Discussion

It is known that biodiverse plant mixtures are more resilient to environmental changes than monocultures (Brooker *et al.*, 2015). Our results showed that four biodiverse plant species mixtures with different proportions of 4–6 species belonging to *Leguminosae* and *Gramineae* families differed

on their morphological and physiological behaviour and this was related to their individual species composition. The grasses studied tended to be taller than the legume species in the first 7 weeks of development. This type of early establishment can bring some advantage in the light competition for photosynthesis (Davies, 2001). On the other hand, the legumes analysed presented higher content of photosynthetic pigments than the grasses, which indirectly indicates a better predisposition for light capture and increased photosynthetic rate (Buttery & Buzzell, 1977), and enhanced antioxidant capacity during plant stress (Uarrotá *et al.*, 2018). The plant species mixtures take advantage of those niche complementarities or beneficial interactions, for instance, by maximizing light capture within the mixture, due to different plant architecture or pigments content, or by facilitation of growth through symbiotic N₂ fixation by legumes (Roscher *et al.*, 2016). The four tested mixtures occupied across time an intermediate morphological and physiological position between the legumes (mainly the clovers) and the grasses, essentially due to the influence of the canopy height and plant length. Moreover, the mixtures were distinguishable among themselves by the aerial and root dry weights which were positively correlated with overall biomass. It is known that a prolific root system may be more advantageous to the plant for acquiring water and nutrients especially under limitation situations (Sánchez-Blanco *et al.*, 2014). Moreover, root length is an indicator of the ability of a plant to absorb water from deeper layers of the soil. The observed variation on root traits may be further explored to enhance plants response to water-limiting conditions, increasingly more frequent in the Mediterranean region.

These preliminary results will enable us to further explore the plant-plant complementarities and beneficial interactions identified here, particularly on root architecture and photosynthetic performance, and whether species traits differ when grown in mixtures. This will facilitate the development of innovative plant mixtures that are productive and more resilient to climate change challenges and promote a more ecological and sustainable future grassland agriculture.

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